

Mixed ligand complex formation equilibria of some toxic metal ions with L-phenylalanine and maleic acid in CTAB-water mixtures

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Manuscript received online 30 January 2014, revised 11 March 2014, accepted 23 March 2014

Abstract : The stability constants of ternary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} ions with L-phenylalanine and maleic acid were determined pH metrically in the concentration range of 0.0–2.5% w/v cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB)-water mixtures maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ at 303.0 K. Alkalimetric titrations were carried out in different relative concentrations [M : L : X = 1.0 : 2.5 : 2.5, 1.0 : 2.5 : 5.0, 1.0 : 5.0 : 2.5] of metal (M) to L-phenylalanine (L) to maleic acid (X). Stability constants of ternary complexes were calculated and various models were refined with MINIQUAD75. The best fit chemical models were selected based on statistical parameters and residual analysis. The species detected are MLXH₂, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Pb^{II} and MLX₂H₃, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Cd^{II} and ML₂XH₂, ML₂XH and MLX₂ for Hg^{II}. The relative stabilities of the mixed ligand complexes were compared with those of the binary complexes. The enhanced stability associated with the ternary complex is attributed to chelate effect, stacking interactions and hydrogen bonding.

Keywords : Stability constants, mixed-ligand complexes, L-phenylalanine, maleic acid, CTAB.

Introduction

Investigations of acido-basic equilibria of amino acids, their interaction with metal ions in media of varying ionic strength, temperature and dielectric constant throw light on the mechanism of enzyme-catalyzed reactions. Although it is known that the polarity of the active site cavities in proteins is lower than that of the bulk, a direct measurement of the dielectric constant is not possible. Comparing the formation constants of acido-basic equilibria and/or metal complex equilibria with those at biological centers offers a way to estimate the effective dielectric constant or equivalent solution dielectric constant for the active site cavity¹. This brought a renaissance in the study of complex equilibria in aqua-organic and aquamicellar mixtures apart from its established utility in understanding solute-solvent interactions, increasing sensitivity of reactions of analytical and industrial importance and solubilising ligands or their metal complexes.

Chemical speciation of metals is important for an un-

derstanding of their distribution, mobility, bioavailability, toxicity and for setting environmental quality standards. Bioavailability of a particular metal depends on its complex chemical reactions of dissolution; binding and complexation with the constituents of the environmental aquatic phase². The activity of bacteria increase the concentration of dissolved organic carbon and decreases the pH value of water. This causes an increase in the complexation and mobility of a metal³. Complexation significantly decreases bioavailability.

The main symptoms toxicity of lead in adults are headache, abdominal pain, memory loss, kidney failure, male reproductive problems, and weakness, pain, or tingling in the extremities⁴. Signs of chronic exposure include loss of short-term memory or concentration, depression, nausea, abdominal pain, loss of coordination, numbness and tingling in the extremities⁵. A fetus developing in the womb of a woman who has elevated blood lead level is also susceptible to lead poisoning, and is at

greater risk of being born prematurely or with a low birth weight⁶. Children are more risk for lead poisoning because their smaller bodies are in a continuous state of growth and development⁷. Cadmium is a toxic metal that can cause several health effects⁸, mainly kidney and bone damage, even in none occupationally exposed populations and studies indicate health concerns at low dose of exposure either in adults⁹ or children. Mercury is a toxic metal originating from both anthropogenic and natural sources. Although most of the mercury released in the environment is inorganic or elemental, once in the water, it can be transformed into methyl mercury (MeHg) by microbial action¹⁰. This highly toxic form of mercury is accumulated in animal tissues and is biomagnified in the food chain¹¹. In adults, MeHg mainly affects the nervous system and is also toxic to the kidney, liver, reproductive organs and the cardiovascular system^{12,13}. L-Phenylalanine (Phe) is biologically converted into L-tyrosine. L-Tyrosine in turn is converted into L-DOPA (L-3,4-dihydroxyphenylalanine), which is further converted into dopamine, nor epinephrine and epinephrine. Phenylalanine is converted to cinnamic acid by the action of enzyme phenylalanine ammonia-lyase¹⁴. Phenylalanine uses the same active transport channel as tryptophan to cross the blood-brain barrier, and in large quantities, interferes with the production of serotonin. Industrially maleic acid (MA) is derived by hydrolysis of maleic anhydride. Maleic acid is the raw material for the production of glyoxylic acid which used as a key intermediate in the pharma or agro industries (e.g. in the manufacture of vanillin, amoxicillin and fine chemicals). The major industrial use of maleic acid is its conversion to fumaric acid. Maleic acid and fumaric acid do not spontaneously interconvert because rotation around a carbon carbon double bond is not energetically favorable. However, it is possible by photolysis in the presence of a small amount of bromine.

Micelles alter the reaction rates and shift equilibria primarily by concentrating reactants within the small volume of micellar pseudo phase. The extent of change is a product of the micellar effect on the reaction within the micellar pseudo phase and the distribution of reactants between the two phases. The effect of micelles on overall reaction rates and equilibria depends upon the incorporation of solutes into the micellar pseudo phase. CTAB is a cationic surfactant which tends to denature proteins and

profoundly influences the bulk properties of physiological systems. It can solubilise, concentrate and compartmentalize ions and molecules¹⁵. Hence, the influence of cationic micellar media (CTAB) on the chemical speciation of ternary complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with L-phenylalanine and maleic acid has been investigated. Protonation constants of Phe and MA¹⁶ and their binary complexes with toxic metals in CTAB-water mixture have already been studied in this laboratory^{17,18}.

Experimental

0.05 mol L⁻¹ solutions of L-phenylalanine (Loba, India) and maleic acid (Loba, India) were prepared in deionised triple-distilled water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid concentration to increase the solubility. CTAB (Merck, India) was used as received. Sodium nitrate (Qualigens, India) of 2 mol L⁻¹ was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. Solutions of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} nitrates (0.1 mol L⁻¹) were prepared by dissolving appropriate quantities of G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ acid (HNO₃) to suppresses the hydrolysis of metal ions. Nitric acid (Merck, India) of 0.2 mol L⁻¹ and sodium hydroxide (Merck, India) of 0.4 mol L⁻¹ were also prepared. All these solutions were standardized using standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification¹⁹. The strengths of the alkali and the mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{20,21}.

Procedure :

For titrimetric data ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01) was used. The effect of variations in asymmetry, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted in the form of correction factor²²⁻²⁴. For the determination of stability constants of ternary species, initially, strong acid was titrated against alkali at regular intervals to check the completion of the equilibration of the glass electrode. Then, the calomel electrode was refilled with CTAB-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of the titrand. All the titrations were performed in medium containing varying concentrations of CTAB-water mixtures (0.0-2.5% w/v) pH metrically at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. In each of the

titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 cm³. Titrations were carried out in the presence of different relative concentrations of the metal ion to Phe (L) and MA (X) with 0.4 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. The concentrations of the ingredients are given in Table 1. The details of the experimental procedure and the titration assembly were given elsewhere²⁵⁻²⁷.

Results and discussion

Titration curves :

For the present work different set of titrations were titrated separately with standard NaOH solution these titration curves are given in Fig. 1. These curves were best evidence for formation of ternary species in the solution.

From this Figure reveals that :

- (i) A decrease in pH when the ligand (L/X) is added to the free acid solution suggests that the release of protons due to deprotonation of protonated ligands prepared in acidic media (0.05 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃). In
- (ii) Metal ligand curves (ML/MX) shows lower pH comparing their protonation curves indicating formation of metal ligand complex species and release of protons.

Fig. 1. Titration curves (M = Pb, L = Phe, X = MA and FA = HNO₃).

this titration curve of MA (X) shows lower pH due to more protons from deprotonation of protonated ligands compared to Phe (L).

Table 1. Total initial concentrations of ingredients (in mmol) for mixed ligand titrations in CTAB-water mixtures [NaOH] = 0.4 mol L⁻¹; V₀ = 50.0 cm³; temp = 303 K; ionic strength = 0.16 mol L⁻¹; mineral acid = 1 mmol M = Pb^{II}/Cd^{II}/Hg^{II}; L = Phe; X = MA

% (w/v) CTAB	TM0			TL0		C _M : C _L : C _X
	Pb ^{II}	Cd ^{II}	Hg ^{II}	Phe	MA	
0.0	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.2494	0.2498	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
				0.3741	0.3747	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4988	0.4996	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
0.5	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.2478	0.2484	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
				0.3717	0.3726	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4956	0.4968	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
1.0	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.2494	0.2489	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
				0.3741	0.3733	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4988	0.4878	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
1.5	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.2493	0.2495	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
				0.3739	0.3742	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4986	0.4990	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
2.0	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.2488	0.2503	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
				0.3732	0.3754	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4976	0.5006	1 : 2.5 : 5.0
2.5	0.1023	0.1013	0.1002	0.2483	0.2505	1 : 2.5 : 2.5
				0.3724	0.3757	1 : 5.0 : 2.5
				0.4966	0.5010	1 : 2.5 : 5.0

*TL0 = Initial total ligand concentration, TM0 = Initial total metal concentration, C_M : Concentration of metal, C_L : Concentration of primary ligand, C_X : Concentration of secondary ligand.

- (iii) The mixed-ligand (MLX) curve lie below the pure ligand as well as those of binary metal ligand curves indicating the formation of ternary complex species and release of more protons.
- (iv) Since the mixed-ligand curve did not coincide with either of the individual metal titration curves in the lower pH range, the formation of complex by simultaneous equilibria was inferred.
- (v) The formation of mixed complex species in solution was supported by absence of any solid phase during the titration of ternary mixture.

Modeling of chemical speciation :

A preliminary investigation of alkalimetric titrations of mixtures containing different mole ratios of Phe and MA in the presence of mineral acid and inert electrolyte inferred that no condensed species were formed. The protonation¹⁶ constants and the stability constants of the binary^{17,18} metal complexes of these ligands were fixed in

refining of ternary complexes and in testing various chemical models using MINIQUAD75. The best fit models were chosen based on the statistical parameters²⁸ like χ^2 , *R*-factor, skewness and kurtosis given in Table 2. The ternary complex species detected are MLXH₂, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Pb^{II} and MLX₂H₃, ML₂XH₂ and ML₂XH for Cd^{II} and ML₂XH₂, ML₂XH and MLX₂ for Hg^{II}. A very low standard deviation (SD) in log values of overall stability constants (log β) indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of *U*_{corr} (sum of squares of deviations in the concentrations of the ligands and the hydrogen ion under experimental conditions) corrected for degrees of freedom, indicate that the models represent the experimental data. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of kurtosis and skewness should be three and zero, respectively. The kurtosis values, in the present study

Table 2. Parameters of best-fit chemical models of Phe and MA complexes of Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} in CTAB-water mixtures

% w/v CTAB	log β (SD)					pH-range	NP	<i>U</i> _{corr}	χ^2	Skewness	Kurtosis	<i>R</i> -factor
	MLXH ₂	ML ₂ XH	ML ₂ XH ₂	MLX ₂ H ₃	MLX ₂							
Pb ^{II}												
0.0	22.36(20)	22.29(39)	28.71(22)	-	-	3.0-8.7	54	20.49	36.59	1.03	8.18	0.0832
0.5	22.03(58)	21.83(58)	28.37(50)	-	-	3.0-7.5	26	6.956	3.04	-0.55	5.00	0.0181
1.0	22.01(44)	21.19(59)	27.41(58)	-	-	3.0-7.5	32	8.620	7.50	-0.43	3.04	0.0205
1.5	22.38(20)	20.60(33)	27.73(26)	-	-	3.0-7.5	26	2.173	28.00	-1.00	9.88	0.0109
2.0	21.57(34)	20.15(51)	27.18(49)	-	-	3.0-7.5	34	9.354	20.59	0.10	4.97	0.0216
2.5	20.73(32)	20.01(46)	26.84(44)	-	-	3.0-7.5	39	16.38	21.37	-0.61	6.01	0.0300
Cd ^{II}												
0.0	-	21.96(39)	28.92(48)	30.55(46)	-	3.0-9.0	55	37.46	22.33	1.18	6.94	0.0829
0.5	-	22.92(60)	28.36(57)	30.73(72)	-	3.0-7.5	29	4.615	3.17	0.53	3.63	0.0161
1.0	-	21.60(42)	27.73(38)	30.33(34)	-	3.0-7.5	33	5.333	7.27	-0.22	4.18	0.0175
1.5	-	21.46(60)	27.99(53)	30.10(52)	-	3.0-7.5	32	31.57	20.41	-0.04	12.43	0.0383
2.0	-	19.59(34)	25.84(50)	29.01(19)	-	3.0-7.5	36	30.87	36.78	0.38	4.88	0.0225
2.5	-	19.20(24)	25.73(33)	29.34(09)	-	3.0-7.5	34	30.70	11.76	0.30	5.03	0.0146
Hg ^{II}												
0.0	-	22.86(16)	28.52(05)	-	13.44(09)	2.4-6.9	27	0.555	8.00	0.39	3.39	0.0032
0.5	-	23.80(37)	29.36(17)	-	15.44(16)	3.0-6.9	25	7.368	15.05	0.43	4.03	0.0203
1.0	-	23.99(54)	30.25(45)	-	14.16(63)	3.0-6.9	26	6.315	3.82	-0.04	3.04	0.0172
1.5	-	23.42(37)	29.37(34)	-	14.21(36)	3.0-6.9	24	03.55	1.91	-0.15	2.94	0.0138
2.0	-	23.52(50)	29.37(51)	-	14.41(49)	3.0-6.9	25	07.27	2.24	-0.18	2.84	0.0194
2.5	-	23.63(23)	28.88(29)	-	15.13(19)	3.0-6.9	26	56.52	1.38	0.23	2.83	0.0167

*U*_{corr} = *U*/(NP - m) × 10⁸; NP = Number of points; m = number of constants; SD = standard deviation, β = Stability constant.

indicate that some of the residuals are nearer to mesokurtic and other form leptokurtic patterns. The values of skewness recorded in Table 2 are between -1.00 and 1.18 . This data evince that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, the least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The suitability of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic R -values recorded.

Effect of surfactant on the stability of ternary complexes :

Many workers were opinion that both electrostatic and non-electrostatic effects should be considered even in the case of simple acido-basic equilibria; one dominates the other, depending upon the nature of solute and solvent²⁹⁻³¹. Born's classical treatment³² holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change. The effect of surfactant on complex equilibria and appar-

ent shift in the magnitude of stability constants in micellar media can be attributed³³ to the creation of a concentration gradient of proton between the interface and the bulk solution. The number of micelles increases with the concentration of surfactant, and oppositely charged ions are concentrated in the Stern layer³⁴. CTAB has a positive polar head and hence, negatively charged ligand ions are concentrated in the Stern layer where as hydrogen ions are pushed into the bulk solvent. The deprotonated carboxyl ions are stabilized compared to the protonated forms by the cationic micelles due to the formation of ion pairs. The stability constants ($\log \beta$) varied linearly with mole fraction of CTAB due to the polarity of the medium, charge on the micellar surface and due to the electrostatic forces/hydrophobic interactions operating between the complex species and micellar surface. The species are stabilized in the micellar medium with opposite charges

Fig. 2. Variation of magnitude of stability constant ($\log \beta$) of ternary complexes of Phe-MA with mole fraction ($n_x \times 10^3$) of CTAB : (A) Pb^{II}, (B) Cd^{II}, (C) Hg^{II} : (\circ) $\log \beta_{ML_2XH}$, (Δ) $\log \beta_{ML_2XH_2}$, (\star) $\log \beta_{MLXH_2}$, (\square) $\log \beta_{MLX_2H_3}$, (\diamond) $\log \beta_{MLX_2}$, respectively.

due to electrostatic interactions. The linear or almost linear variations of stability constants ($\log \beta$) with the mole fraction of CTAB (Fig. 2) indicate the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces^{35,36}. The non-linearity may be due to the relative contributions of the structure-forming nature and complexing ability of CTAB. One of the reasons for such behavior is accumulation of metal ion and ligand on the surface of the micelles with increased concentration of surfactant.

Stability of ternary complexes :

The formation of mononuclear unprotonated binary and ternary complexes from a mixture of metal ion (M) and primary (L) and secondary (X) ligands can be shown as the equilibria given in eq. (1). The change in the stability of the ternary complexes as compared to their binary analogues was quantified³⁷⁻⁴⁰ based on the disproportionation constant ($\log X$) given by eq. (2).

$$\log X = 2 \log K_{MLX}^M - \log K_{ML_2}^M - \log K_{MX_2}^M \quad (2)$$

This corresponds to the equilibrium

Under these equilibrium conditions one can expect 50% ternary complex and 25% each of the binary complexes to be formed and the value of $\log X$ was reported to be 0.6⁴². A value greater than this accounts for the extra stability of MLX.

Another approach^{39,41,42} to quantify the stability of ternary complexes was based on the difference in stability ($\Delta \log K$) for the reactions ML with X and M_(aq) with L and X, where L is primary ligand and X is the secondary ligand. It is compared with that calculated purely on statistical grounds. Eq. (3) can be formulated based on the properties of the cyclic systems reported earlier^{43,44} from which it is clear that both the ligands in the ternary complex influence mutually to the same extent.

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MLX}^M - \log K_{ML}^M - \log K_M^M \quad (3)$$

The electrostatic theory of binary complex formation and statistical arguments suggest the additional coordination positions of given multivalent hydrated metal ion available for the first ligand than for the second. Hence, the usual order of stability $K_{ML}^M > K_{MLX}^{ML}$ applies. This suggests that $\Delta \log K$ should be negative, although several exceptions⁴⁵ have been found. The statistical values of $\Delta \log K$ for bidentate L and X are -0.4, -0.6 and between -0.9 and -0.3 for octahedral, square planar and distorted octahedral complexes, respectively. Negative values of $\Delta \log K$ can be understood as the secondary ligand forms a more stable complex with hydrated metal ion than with ML.

Whenever the experimental values of $\Delta \log K$ exceed the statistical values, it can be inferred that the ternary complex is formed as a result of interaction of ML with X or MX with L. $\Delta \log K$ values of ternary complexes containing bipyridyl as the primary ligand are positive³⁹ for O-donors (malonic acid, pyrocatechol etc.), negative⁴³ for N-donors (ethylene diamine) and intermediate or negative⁴⁶ for amino acids with both N and O coordination sites. However, a very high negative value (-2.3) for Cu(en)(iminodiacetic acid) and a positive value (0.82) for Cu(o-phen)-(6,7-dihydroxynaphthaline-2-sulphonate) was also observed³⁷.

The $\Delta \log K$ values calculated from binary and ternary complexes and the equations for the calculation of $\Delta \log K$ are given in Table 3. These values could not be calculated for some of the systems due to the absence of relevant binary species. In the present study, $\Delta \log K$ values are in the range from -8.14 to 2.98 which indicate that the ternary complexes formed by the Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} were more stable compared to Hg^{II}. The reason for the extra stability of these complexes may be due to (i) the interactions outside the coordination sphere such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, (ii) charge neutralization, (iii) chelate effect and (iv) stacking interactions^{47,48}.

Effect of influential parameters on stability constants :

Any error in the parameters like concentrations of ingredients affects the magnitudes of equilibrium constant estimates. Such parameters are called influential

Table 3. $\Delta \log K$ values of ternary complexes of Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} -Phe and MA in CTAB-water mixtures and the corresponding equations used in the calculations

% w/v CTAB	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MLXH}_2}$	$\Delta \log K_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}}$	$\Delta \log K_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}_2}$	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MLX}_2}$
		Pb^{II}		
0.0	-4.28	0.61	2.07	-
0.5	-4.61	0.28	1.73	-
1.0	-5.48	-0.07	-0.08	-
1.5	-4.26	-0.14	1.09	-
2.0	-5.75	-1.27	-0.14	-
2.5	-5.95	-1.66	0.16	-
		Cd^{II}		
0.0	-	0.55	2.54	-
0.5	-	1.55	1.35	-
1.0	-	0.69	1.3	-
1.5	-	0.79	1.47	-
2.0	-	-1.7	-1.23	-
2.5	-	-1.55	-0.77	-
		Hg^{II}		
0.0	-	0.59	0.43	-8.14
0.5	-	2.34	2.15	-5.58
1.0	-	2.98	3.74	-6.86
1.5	-	2.43	3.62	-6.58
2.0	-	2.5	2.67	-6.8
2.5	-	2.81	2.32	-5.96
	Equations for calculation of $\Delta \log K$			
	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MLXH}_2} = \log \beta_{\text{MLXH}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{MX}_2\text{H}}$			
	$\Delta \log K_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}} = \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}} - \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{MX}_2}$			
	$\Delta \log K_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}_2} = \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{MX}_2\text{H}}$			
	$\Delta \log K_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}_2} = \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{XH}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{MX}_2\text{H}}$			
	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MLX}_2} = \log \beta_{\text{MLX}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{MX}_2}$			
	$\Delta \log K_{\text{MLX}_2} = \log \beta_{\text{MLX}_2} - \log \beta_{\text{ML}_2\text{H}} - \log \beta_{\text{MX}_3}$			

parameters. In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was carried out by introducing errors into the concentrations of alkali, acid, ligands, metal and correction factors. The results of typical samples given in Table 4 emphasize that the errors in the concentrations of alkali and acid affect stability constant estimates more than those of the ligands and metal.

Chemical speciation :

Distribution diagrams drawn using the formation constants of the best fit model are shown in Fig. 3 which

contain protonated and unprotonated species like MLXH_2 , ML_2XH and ML_2XH_2 for Pb^{II} and ML_2XH , ML_2XH_2 and MLX_2H_3 for Cd^{II} and ML_2XH , ML_2XH_2 and MLX_2 for Hg^{II} . The distribution diagrams indicate the relative abundance of various forms of metal ions (chemical speciation) at different pH and dielectric conditions. A stable ternary complex shall be responsible for metal ion transportation in bio-systems and the weak binary metal complexes make the essential metals bioavailable. The increased concentrations of complexing agents make the essential metal ions unavailable due to the formation of stable complexes. The formation of the possible complex

Table 4. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with Phe-MA in 1.0% (w/v) CTAB-water mixture

Ingredient	% Error	log β _{mlxh} (SD)		
		1211	1212	1123
Alkali	0	21.60(42)	27.73(38)	30.33(34)
	-5	Rejected	26.81(53)	31.58(23)
	-2	19.44(37)	26.36(46)	30.32(45)
	+2	Rejected	26.12(65)	Rejected
	+5	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
Acid	-5	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	23.75(91)	29.43(94)	Rejected
	+2	19.20(17)	26.10(18)	30.29(06)
	+5	16.96(92)	25.82(43)	30.75(11)
Ligand (L)	-5	21.69(43)	27.81(39)	30.37(35)
	-2	21.64(42)	27.76(39)	30.34(34)
	+2	21.57(42)	27.69(38)	30.31(34)
	+5	21.53(42)	27.66(38)	30.29(34)
Ligand (X)	-5	23.02(92)	28.77(94)	30.70(95)
	-2	22.19(56)	28.15(51)	30.46(54)
	+2	21.13(31)	27.41(29)	30.26(22)
	+5	20.59(22)	27.11(21)	30.28(13)
Metal	-5	21.83(51)	27.85(46)	30.37(45)
	-2	21.68(45)	27.76(41)	30.34(38)
	+2	21.50(40)	27.67(36)	30.30(31)
	+5	21.38(36)	27.60(33)	30.29(28)
log F	-5	21.55(41)	27.69(37)	30.33(33)
	-2	21.57(42)	27.70(38)	30.32(34)
	+2	21.61(43)	27.72(39)	30.31(35)
	+5	21.63(43)	27.74(39)	30.31(36)
Volume	-5	21.62(44)	27.75(40)	30.35(36)
	-2	21.61(43)	27.74(39)	30.34(35)
	+2	21.59(42)	27.72(38)	30.32(34)
	+5	21.58(44)	27.71(40)	30.31(36)

*β = Stability constant, SD = Standard deviation.

species can be represented by the following equilibria.

Fig. 3. Species distribution diagrams of ternary complexes of Phe and MA; (A) Pb^{II} , (B) Cd^{II} and (C) Hg^{II} in 1.0% w/v CTAB-water mixture.

Some typical distribution diagrams in 1.0% CTAB-water mixture are shown in Fig. 3. Fig. 3(A) shows the formation of Pb^{II} -Phe-MA complexes, $MLXH_2$, ML_2XH_2 and ML_2XH in the pH range 2.0–9.0, in this range total metal ion participate in bonding. At lower pH the species $MLXH_2$ had high concentration (Equilibria 4). As the pH increases the concentration of $MLXH_2$, LH_2^+ and XH_2 decreased and the concentration of ML_2XH_2 and ML_2XH were increased (Equilibria 5, 6, 9, 10 and 11). Above pH value 5.0, the concentration of ML_2XH_2 species decreases with increasing ML_2XH species indicates that ML_2XH forms through the (Equilibria 8, 12, 13 and 14).

Fig. 3(B) shows the formation of Cd^{II} -Phe-MA complexes, MLX_2H_3 , ML_2XH_2 and ML_2XH in the pH range 2.0–9.0. At lower pH value the concentration of MLX_2H_3 is high (Equilibria 15). As the pH value increases the concentration of MLX_2H_3 decreases with increasing the

concentration of ML_2XH_2 species (Equilibrium 5 and 6). Above 5.0 pH value ML_2XH complex formed while the XH_2 and MX_2H species decreased (Equilibria 13 and 14).

Fig. 3(C) shows the formation of Hg^{II} -Phe-MA complexes, ML_2XH_2 , ML_2XH and MLX_2 in the pH range 2.0–8.0. At lower pH the species ML_2XH_2 had high concentration (Equilibria 5 and 6). As the pH increases the concentration of $MLXH_2$, LH_2^+ and XH_2 decreased and the concentration of ML_2XH is increases (Equilibria 8, 9 and 10). Above pH value 6.0, MLX_2 species has high concentration (Equilibria 16 and 17).

Structures :

Depending upon the nature of the ligands and the metal ions and based on the basic chemical knowledge the structures of the ternary complexes were proposed as shown in Fig. 4. These structures indicate that phenylalanine and maleic acid act as monodentate or bidentate ligand

Fig. 4. Proposed structures of ternary complexes of phenylalanine and maleic acid, where S is either solvent or water molecule.

depending upon the pH conditions. In highly acidic medium the amino group of L-phenylalanine is protonated and do not participate in coordination as shown in the structure of MLX_2H_3 , $MLXH_2$ and ML_2XH_2 . In ML_2XH_2 species phenylalanine act as monodentate and maleic acid acts as bidentate. In mono protonated ternary complexes like ML_2XH , phenylalanine acts as mono and bidentate ligand and maleic acid act as only bidentate and the proton is on phenylalanine but not on maleic acid. So, the species is $M(L_2H)X$ but not $M(L_2)(XH)$.

Conclusions

The following conclusions have been drawn from the modeling studies of the speciation of ternary complexes of Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with phenylalanine and maleic acid in CTAB-water media :

(i) The ternary metal complex species detected are

$MLXH_2$, ML_2XH_2 and ML_2XH for Pb^{II} and MLX_2H_3 , ML_2XH_2 and ML_2XH for Cd^{II} and ML_2XH_2 , ML_2XH and MLX_2 for Hg^{II} . Where L = Phe and X = MA. Only these species are refined due to the restricted pH ranges and the possible active forms of ligands like LH_2^+ , LH, and XH_2 , XH^- for L-phenylalanine and maleic acid, respectively.

(ii) The values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate that the ternary species have extra stability compared to the binary species, may be due to the interactions outside the coordination sphere, such as the formation of hydrogen bonds between the coordinated ligands, charge neutralization, chelate effect, stacking interactions and the electrostatic interaction between non-coordinated charge groups of the ligands.

- (iii) The linear almost linear variation in the stabilities of ternary complexes with increasing mole fraction of the surfactant is due to the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.
- (iv) The magnitude of the stability constants for mixed ligand complexes are affected by the errors in the influential parameters like concentration of ingredients. The order of influence is alkali > acid > MA > Phe > metal ion > log *F* > volume.
- (v) The study also gives an insight into the metal availability/metal transport in biofluids. The ternary complexes are more amenable for "metal transport" because of their extra stability.

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